

MICROBE
the Microbiome
Biobanking (RI)
Enabler

2nd MICROBE project newsletter (July 2024)

Dear colleagues, friends and innovators,

Welcome to our second project update! We are thrilled to share the latest developments and milestones with you. In this edition, you'll find:

- Successful conclusion of our first review period and progress on our initial milestones
- MICROBE Experts Campaign - Introduction to talented MICROBE researchers
- Highlights from our recent project meeting in Roscoff, France
- MICROBE's participation in several key conferences, including one in Torino

In April 2024 we submitted our 1st periodic report taking into account the 1st project year of MICROBE. The project review stated that considerable progress has been achieved in line with the expected timeframe and that the project is on target to reach to reach its exciting, expected objectives.

MICROBE focuses on eight main objectives

1. Develop innovative strategies and protocols for the preservation and storage of microbiome samples
2. Develop novel methods for the isolation and co-cultivation of complex microbial communities
3. Develop novel approaches for the assessment of the key functions of microbiomes
4. Develop an operational framework for microbiome biobanking
5. Validate developed approaches
6. Provide recommendations for a legal and ethical framework for microbiome biobanking
7. Develop and deliver training on novel approaches
8. Elaborate new business opportunities for research infrastructures and their users

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Expected MICROBE project results

- validated protocols for preserving and propagating complex microbiome samples
- novel isolates of members of key microbiomes from different domains
- novel synthetic consortia reproducing key functionalities of selected ecosystems
- customised data infrastructure tools for microbiome biobanking
- guidelines for pre-analytical microbiome sample quality and metadata for standardised microbiome biobanking workflows in selected fields
- guidelines for establishing ethical and legal framework conditions enabling microbiome biobanking
- business models for implementing and exploiting novel microbiome-based technologies and resources
- training and educational activities

MICROBE Experts Campaign

MICROBE has designed a MICROBE Experts Campaign to promote the persons behind MICROBE. The campaign is based on the teams of each project beneficiary and also focuses on promoting our young researchers and colleagues in their workspace. We therefore design videos, photos and personal statements that are shared via the MICROBE's social media channels and YouTube. The media will also be available on the MICROBE website. We started with the AIT Team in our 1st newsletter and a video with Sara Pipponzi PhD.

In this 2nd newsletter, we go on with our team and colleagues from our project beneficiary Medical University of Graz, Austria, (MUG). We present here our two experts Mag. Cornelia Stumptner and Dr. Katrin Panzitt.

Dr. Katrin Panzitt

My name is Katrin Panzitt (*left side*). My main activity in the MICROBE project is in the investigation and preservation of the microbial nucleic acids of different use cases. At the Medical University of Graz we are mainly interested in the human microbiome but the MICROBE project has a strong emphasis on environmental microbiomes. In this project we were able to extend our interest to an environmental microbiome, namely the soil microbiome. We also implemented a new sequencing technique, the long read sequencing technique, on the soil use case for the first time. In the future of the MICROBE project we will go on to investigate human microbiomes other than the gut microbiome with a special emphasis on the presence of viruses. For me, the microbiome - may it be human or environmental - with all its functions, adaptability and interconnectedness still surprises me! I love the MICROBE project because it has such a broad scope and tries to answer super relevant question of this time.

Mag. Cornelia Stumptner

My name is Cornelia Stumptner (*right side*) and In MICROBE project I am leading WP4 Standardization and QC, which develops requirements for pre-analytical sample quality and metadata - a topic that is highly relevant for research and biobanking. As executive manager of BBMRI.at (the Austrian node of the European Biobanking Research Infrastructure BBMRI-ERIC, I have long experience in the biobanking field and a leading role in developing sample pre-analytics standards for human microbiome specimens (CEN/TS17626; ISO 18701). MICROBE meets three of my personal interests: biobanking, sample quality & standards, and microbiome.

Link to the MICROBE website and related interview videos: [MICROBE Videos](#)

MICROBE aims to set up a community of relevant experts outside our consortium. Experts in the field of

- microbiome research
- preservation of microbes
- isolation of microbes
- storage and re-use of microbes
- human environments of microbiomes
- soil environments of microbiomes
- seed environments of microbiomes
- marine environments of microbiomes
- pre-analytical sample quality and metadata requirements

We invite you to register to our MICROBE Community and actively work with us.

Follow us!

Visit our website and register to our MICROBE Community

MICROBE events and news

Here, we present MICROBE events and workshops as well as events related to the areas we are working in.

MICROBE meeting in Roscoff, France

17th - 19th April 2024

The 1st annual consortium meeting has taken place in Roscoff, France. Thanks to our project partner Sorbonne University we had a really nice location and successful meeting. We started the meeting by sharing overviews of progress made in each workpackage, which has been mainly presented by our young researchers.

Further on, the work package Leaders organised interactive sessions to plan and define the next steps for the second project year. One session has been dedicated to discussing and reviewing of existing/upcoming data and data linkages and how to use these in the publications.

On the second day, a session on pre-analytical standards and the planning of a related publication was organised, followed by a session on regulatory and business modeling. Finally, the engagement of stakeholders and advisory group members and collaborations with other projects were addressed.

MICROBE at European Biobank Week and EMBL Workshop

MICROBE has been presented at these two selected events with posters and talks in May 2024.

Sara Pippozzi (AIT), Miguel Bonin (CABI) and Cornelia Stumptner (MUG) presented MICROBE by interesting posters and talks.

MIRCOBE project details

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